

1 **Supplemental Materials for “Modeling Long-Term Flow Regimes in**
2 **Ungauged Basins: An Evaluation of Machine Learning Performance and**
3 **Uncertainty”**

4 **Supplement 3: Methodological Details**

5 immediate

6 **METHODOLOGICAL DETAILS**

7 **Feature selection**

8 From the 62 initial variables, we first excluded the variables with missing or no-coverage values
9 in the catchments analyzed (ST_{Si} , LT_{Ev} , and LT_{Ig}), resulting in 59 environmental descriptors.
10 Hierarchical clustering was then employed for feature selection, as described by Johnson 1967. This
11 technique involves grouping similar data points into clusters, visualized through a dendrogram, a
12 tree-like structure. In feature selection, hierarchical clustering aids in identifying groups of similar
13 features for potential combination or removal while preserving the original descriptors. The process
14 begins with the creation of a correlation matrix, using the Spearman correlation coefficient to
15 capture monotonic descriptor-to-descriptor associations. This matrix displays pairwise correlations
16 between all features. Following this, features were clustered based on descriptor-to-descriptor
17 distances defined as one minus the absolute Spearman correlation, using average linkage. The
18 dendrogram helped in deciding the level at which to cut and form the final feature clusters. The
19 number of clusters chosen depended on the chosen dendrogram cut-off distance.

20 Feature selection within each cluster was then carried out. The representative feature was
21 determined as the most central descriptor in the cluster, i.e., the descriptor with the minimum
22 average distance to the other members of the same cluster. No association with q_m or q_{95} was
23 used to select representative descriptors in the revised analysis. The process of selecting the

24 cutting threshold for the dendrogram was iterative, focusing on model performance and ensuring
25 the remaining features were representative of the dataset and not correlated with each other, with
26 the criteria focusing on maintaining features with pairwise Spearman absolute correlation below
27 0.75 and with no decrease in model performance on predicted values. This method ensured the
28 inclusion of representative variables while reducing multicollinearity and preserving interpretable
29 descriptors for later feature-importance analysis. Feature clustering, representative-descriptor
30 selection, and min-max normalization were performed once before cross-validation as descriptor-
31 only preprocessing steps. The normalized predictors were then used for all machine learning (ML)
32 models.

33 **Machine Learning models**

34 Six ML models for regression were tested in this study. They are presented in this section
35 in ascending order of complexity and computational demand, with the simpler models (first two)
36 used as benchmarks for the more complex ones. Multiple linear regression (MLR) and decision
37 trees (DT) were the first two models tested, followed by K-nearest neighbors (KNN), support vector
38 machines (SVM), gradient boosting machine (GBM), and random forest (RF). For a comprehensive
39 understanding of the models, including their mathematical foundations, see [Kuhn and Johnson 2013](#)
40 and [Shalev-Shwartz and Ben-David 2014](#). The models were implemented using the scikit-learn
41 library in Python. Each model was evaluated using the same nested cross-validation framework
42 to ensure a fair comparison of their performance in predicting the target variables based on the
43 selected environmental descriptors.

44 **Nested K-Fold Cross Validation**

45 A nested k-fold cross-validation (CV) approach was used to evaluate the performance of the
46 models. This technique ensures all data are used for training, validation, and testing, minimizing
47 overfitting and underfitting ([Scheda and Diciotti 2022](#)). A schematic view of the method, as used
48 here, can be seen in Figure S3.1. The approach involves using two nested loops: an outer loop
49 for model performance and feature importance evaluations and an inner loop for hyperparameter
50 tuning. In the outer loop, the dataset is divided into k folds, with each fold serving as the test set

51 once while the remaining $k - 1$ folds are used for training. For each training set from the outer
52 loop, the inner loop performs another k -fold CV, splitting the training data into k folds, where one
53 fold is for validation and the remaining $k - 1$ folds are for training. Hyperparameters are tuned
54 based on the performance on the inner validation set, and this process is repeated k times. The
55 best hyperparameters are selected based on the average performance across the inner validation
56 folds, and the model is retrained on the entire outer training set using these hyperparameters. The
57 performance is then evaluated on the outer test set. Feature importances are then evaluated using
58 the leave-one-covariate-out procedure described in section S0. The final prediction values and
59 feature importances are those obtained from each outer test fold. This method helps obtain an
60 unbiased estimate of model performance and prevents overfitting, especially in small datasets. In
61 this study, we used 10 outer folds and 10 inner folds.

62 **Hyperparameter tuning**

63 Hyperparameter tuning was performed using a randomized search cross-validation approach
64 (Bergstra and Bengio 2012). The approach consists of randomly sampling hyperparameters from
65 the ML model using a specified distribution and evaluating model performance for each set of
66 hyperparameters using cross-validation. This cross-validation here refers to the inner 10 folds used
67 on the training set for each outer iteration, as outlined in the modeling overview. For each model,
68 target variable, and outer-fold training set, 100 hyperparameter combinations were sampled and
69 evaluated in the inner cross-validation loop. Randomized search was used because it provides broad
70 coverage of continuous and discrete search spaces at lower computational cost than an exhaustive
71 grid search. The best set of hyperparameters is then selected according to the model's overall
72 performance. The performance metric here was chosen as R^2 (explained in Section S0). The set
73 of distributions for each hyperparameter of each ML model is presented in Table S3.1. The tuned
74 parameters were selected because they control model complexity, neighborhood or kernel behavior,
75 ensemble size, and learning rate; the remaining parameters were kept at the scikit-learn defaults
76 to keep the nested evaluation computationally bounded. After the model hyperparameters were
77 defined, the selected optimal model was fitted to the training data and used to predict the results on

78 the test data.

79 **Running times**

80 Model complexity plays a role in the time taken to run the algorithm. Table S3.2 presents the
81 time required to run the full modeling setup for each model. The machine used to run the models
82 had an i7-8700K CPU with 3.70 GHz, 6 cores, and 64 GB RAM. Overall, comparing running
83 times gives a sense of the relative complexity of each model, but the specific running time depends
84 on the size of the dataset, the complexity of the model, and the specific hyperparameters being
85 used. MLR is the simplest model in the list and has the shortest running time by far, especially
86 because this model does not have hyperparameters to calibrate, which makes it even faster in the
87 comparison. Another relatively time-efficient model is DT, although it is still considerably more
88 complex than linear regression. KNN and SVM come next in degree of complexity, taking between
89 2 and 4 minutes to run. Finally, GBM and RF are the most complex models in the list, which makes
90 them considerably more computationally expensive than the other models, taking around 32 and
91 56 minutes, respectively.

92 **Performance metrics**

93 After the processes covered in the previous section were performed in each one of the 10-fold
94 combinations, the outcomes could be evaluated. To assess the performance of the models, the
95 following statistical metrics were used: the percent bias (BIAS), in %,

$$\text{BIAS} = \frac{\sum(Q_{\text{pred}} - Q_{\text{obs}})}{\sum Q_{\text{obs}}} \times 100 \quad (\text{S1})$$

96 the root mean squared error (RMSE), in $1 \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{km}^{-2}$,

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum(Q_{\text{pred}} - Q_{\text{obs}})^2}{n}} \quad (\text{S2})$$

97 and the predictive coefficient of determination (R^2), dimensionless,

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum(Q_{\text{obs}} - Q_{\text{pred}})^2}{\sum(Q_{\text{obs}} - \bar{Q}_{\text{obs}})^2} \quad (\text{S3})$$

98 where Q_{obs} is the observed unit discharge signature (q_m or q_{95}), and Q_{pred} is the predicted one.

99 **Ensemble construction**

100 Ensemble theory posits that combining multiple models can yield superior predictive perfor-
101 mance compared to relying on a single model (Hu et al. 2015; Sagi and Rokach 2018). This
102 improvement arises because ensembles capture a broader range of patterns and reduce the risk
103 of overfitting by averaging out individual model errors. To verify this premise, all possible com-
104 binations of the 6 models described in the previous section were evaluated. The results of each
105 combination were averaged, and their performance metrics were computed.

106 **Feature importance**

107 Feature importance was evaluated using a leave-one-covariate-out (LOCO) approach, following
108 the model-free variable-importance logic described by Lei et al. 2018. In this approach, the
109 predictive contribution of a covariate is assessed by comparing the performance of the full model
110 with the performance obtained when that covariate is omitted from the predictor set.

111 For each target variable, the full model performance was first established using the selected
112 descriptor set and the cross-validation procedure. Then, each covariate was removed in turn, the
113 modeling workflow was rerun without that covariate, and the resulting held-out predictions were
114 evaluated using R^2 . The importance score of a covariate was computed as the decrease in R^2
115 relative to the full model. Larger decreases therefore indicate covariates whose removal caused
116 greater loss of predictive performance. The resulting rankings therefore identify descriptors that
117 contributed useful predictive information within the adopted modeling workflow.

118 **Uncertainty estimation**

119 Uncertainty was assessed by analyzing the signed errors produced by the selected ensemble
120 model for q_m and q_{95} , defined as $\epsilon = Q_{\text{obs}} - Q_{\text{pred}}$. Under this convention, positive errors indicate

121 model underestimation and negative errors indicate model overestimation. The error diagnostics
122 included errors as a function of the predicted variable, error histograms, Quantile-Quantile plots,
123 and the accumulated variance σ^2 as a function of the magnitude of observed values.

124 After this diagnostic assessment, quantile regression (QR) was used to construct empirical error
125 envelopes as a function of predicted discharge. The objective was to describe how the distribution of
126 signed errors changes with prediction magnitude, rather than to model unsigned error magnitudes.
127 The predicted values were divided into decile intervals, and empirical error quantiles corresponding
128 to central 90% and 75% ranges were computed for each interval. QR models were then fitted using
129 predicted discharge as the independent variable and the signed error as the dependent variable.

130 The resulting QR curves define empirical error envelopes around the model predictions. These
131 envelopes summarize the observed error structure in the cross-validation results and provide ap-
132 proximate error ranges associated with different predicted discharge magnitudes, characterizing the
133 empirical distribution of predictive errors produced by the adopted modeling workflow.

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151 **List of Tables**

152 S3.1 Ranges of hyperparameter values for tuning each ML model. 9

153 S3.2 Running times of each ML model. 10

Model	Parameter	Range*
MLR	–	–
DT	max depth	intU(2, 20)
DT	min samples leaf	intU(5, 100)
KNN	leaf size	intU(1, 50)
KNN	n neighbors	intU(1, 30)
KNN	p	intU(1, 5)
SVM	gamma	logU(0.0001, 1)
SVM	C	logU(0.1, 100)
GBM	n estimators	intU(1, 500)
GBM	max leaf nodes	intU(2, 100)
GBM	learning rate	logU(0.01, 1)
RF	n estimators	intU(1, 500)
RF	max leaf nodes	intU(2, 100)

* *Legend:*

intU: integer-uniform sampling.

logU: log-uniform sampling in the randomized search.

TABLE S3.1. Ranges of hyperparameter values for tuning each ML model.

Model	Running time (mm:ss)
MLR	00:02
DT	00:14
KNN	02:28
SVM	04:01
GBM	31:57
RF	55:53

TABLE S3.2. Running times of each ML model.

154 **List of Figures**

155 S3.1 K-Fold CV 12

Fig. S3.1. — **Nested K-Fold CV.** Approach adopted in this study to evaluate the ML models. Data are divided into k outer folds. In each fold, the training set is divided into k inner folds to tune the hyperparameters of the model. The optimal model of the fold is then tested and evaluated on the test set of the outer fold. Adapted from [Scheda and Diciotti 2022](#).